

Spatial Coherence Report and Demonstration

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Executive summary

This document serves as the report about demonstrations addressing physical coherence across multiple locations in XR. We discuss how scanning and scene understanding descriptions of physical spaces can be used to create a coherent space where multiple remote people can meet. We describe how we use real time tracking data to derive full body avatar movement to be able to naturally walk in the virtual or augmented spaces. We discuss possibilities of using geometric and lighting information of physical spaces to create coherent physics, light and acoustics simulations. Furthermore, we discuss research of a new technique that explores acoustic coherence as style transfer problem with neural networks. Along with technical descriptions we describe 3 demonstrations that illustrate the developed technologies.

The video demonstrations presented are also available on GuestXR's YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/@GuestXR>

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DR	Diminished Reality
HRTF	Head Related Transfer Function
IK	Inverse Kinematics
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
SDK	Software Development Kit
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
SOFA	Spatially Oriented Format for Acoustics
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	Extended Reality

Introduction

This document serves as the report for demonstrations that were given to the public to illustrate spatial and acoustic coherence. Participants visit - embodied as full body avatars - from different remote physical locations in extended reality and naturally interact with each other in each of the participant's local physical space.

1 Content

The document is divided in subsections: 1) First we describe data capture of audio from microphones in the XR headsets and movement data from the VR device's tracking systems; 2) We then discuss locomotion to enable participants to walk as their embodied full body life size avatars; 3) We further define how different physical spaces can be unified and how geometric data extracted from physical spaces can be used to improve interaction and visual appearance; 4) We then examine requirements for sharing remote physical spaces in augmented reality, including requirements for real scene understanding; and finally 5) We discuss possibilities to unify the acoustic model of the different real spaces.

1.1 Movement and voice capture

In this section we describe the types of data that are captured before they are processed and transferred to the shared environment. As in video conferencing systems, VR devices rely on data captured by cameras and microphones. Contrary to video conferencing for shared virtual environments movement data is extracted from the video through computer vision techniques and from accelerometer data. The movement data is processed to provide positional and orientational tracking data of the participant's head and hands and in some cases even fingers and legs. Camera's observing the participant's eyes and face provide data to also extract eye movements and facial expressions as shown in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1 Meta Quest Pro inward facing cameras can track eye movements and facial expressions.

1.1.1 Body movements

To update the participants' viewpoint in the virtual environment according to their real head movements the VR system has to track the head position and orientation of the participants relative to a local frame of reference with high accuracy. Traditionally VR systems relied on external tracking rigs to capture such information. External trackers used to be based on electromagnetic fields, ultrasonic or structured laser light emitters. More recent consumer-oriented headsets are almost entirely vision-based relying mainly on the video stream from the cameras built in the headset. This is now often referred to as inside out tracking as external reference tracking rigs are not required anymore.

The Insight¹ system from Meta for example uses visual inertial simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) techniques to track participants' head movements with high precision. Insight detects image features in the real world and triangulates those points in 3D up to 30 times per second at sub millimetre accuracy. It uses a kinematic prediction algorithm to predict where the user is going to move within a few milliseconds.

Figure 2 Meta's built in inside out tracking system which they call Insight derives the participant's relative head position and orientation based on vision and accelerometer-based data.

Once the insight tracking has computed the participants' head position and orientation, further computer vision techniques which they call constellation tracking are used to derive the position and orientation of the hand controllers. Initially controllers were equipped with infrared LED markers that were detected by the headset cameras.

¹ Powered by AI: Oculus Insight. AR/VR Computer Vision. 22.08.2019 <https://ai.facebook.com/blog/powered-by-ai-oculus-insight/>

Figure 3 Based on infrared LED markers detected by the built-in headset cameras. A vision-based system Meta calls constellation enables the device to compute the participant's hand position and orientation.

In [1] further improvements in computer vision techniques thanks to the progress of machine learning techniques have made it possible to track participants' hands and finger movements even without any additional LED markers and with relatively low processing requirements. These hand tracking methods have been integrated and deployed to the Meta Quest stand-alone headset and are accessible through their Unity Software Development Kit (SDK).

Figure 4 Further advancements in computer vision-based machine learning techniques enables to extract hand positions and orientations also without any additional LED markers and the system can even estimate the movement of each finger segment.

Meta's Quest Pro, Pico Neo 4 Enterprise, the HTC Vive Focus 3 and the upcoming Apple Vision Pro have several additional cameras that observe the participants' eyes and face and enable them to also extract eye and facial movements. The cameras have been upgraded from black and white in the Quest 2 to colour cameras which offer the possibility to merge and reconstruct the video streams from the real environment, which can be overlaid with virtual reality objects to achieve an extended reality system. In addition, on the *Meta's Quest Pro* the controllers have their own 3 cameras to be able to track their position independently of the headset position and potentially to extract more detailed body movements.

2 Reconstruction of the physical environment

In Augmented Reality (AR) the participant sees virtual objects or avatars as if appearing in the real world. In the so-called passthrough mode the cameras video is transformed in real time to be projected to the user's eyes, enabling virtual objects and avatars to be displayed on top of the video feed. In addition, information about the environment must be extracted to be able to place virtual objects in specific locations of the real scene.

2.1 Passthrough

Ideally the cameras' feed could be directly mapped to the display for the participant to see the real world. Since the cameras are differently located than the user's eyes, their images need to be mapped accordingly to not cause motion sickness. Methods and algorithms that are used on the Meta Quest devices have been described in [2].

Figure 5 Quest Headset, camera orientation (blue) vs user viewing direction (orange). Images must be transformed to avoid optical distortions and motion sickness

2.2 Room Geometry and Object extraction

With the *Meta Quest 3* and *Quest 3S* series, a LIDAR sensor has been integrated that enables the user to scan the 3D geometry of the room where the Quest is used. The room scanning functionality is provided by the Meta Space Setup settings configuration. An example screenshot from the room scanning process that shows the 3D mesh overlaid to the real world passthrough imagery is shown in *Figure 6*. In addition to the raw mesh, the system also extracts higher level information about the room such as the location of windows and furniture as depicted in *Figure 7* and *Figure 8*.

Figure 6 Space setup settings show the 3D mesh extracted through the Meta Quest 3 LIDAR sensor.

Figure 7 Meta's Space setup functionality also derives higher level information about the room, such as the location of walls and windows, etc.

Figure 8 Additional higher-level information from the Space setup includes tables, chairs and screens.

2.3 Lighting

While Meta’s AR SDKs do not yet offer a possibility to estimate a light probe, other AR SDKs such as Google’s ARCore and Apple’s ARKit do provide such functionality. In the case of ARCore an estimate of the illumination can be made. Unity integrates the different Vendors’ SDKs in the ARFoundation package. An example of environment probes extracted in real time from an Android smartphone’s camera feed can be seen in *Figure 9*

Figure 9 Environment probes estimated by ARCore from a smartphone camera image. Unity ARFoundations example.

ARCore light estimation is based on research published in [3], [4].

2.4 Physics

Given the possibility to extract a 3D room mesh from the LIDAR scanned room of *Meta Quest 3* and *3S* devices it is straight forward to carry out game physics simulations.

Figure 10 Once the Space setup is complete Meta's SDKs enable the developer to exploit this information for example to carry out physics simulation including collision detection with the 3D mesh of the scanned room. An example here with different coloured balls.

An example app that exploits the extracted room mesh for a physics simulation in AR² which also offers the possibility to store the mesh and furniture information in a JSON file. Unfortunately, the extraction of room 3D meshes is only available with AR Foundation 6, which in turn is only available since October 2024 in Unity 6; and we have found several issues with building our app with that combination of Unity and ARFoundation versions. These issues will likely be resolved by Unity in upcoming updates, and we will be able to build a new version of our app with these added capabilities.

2.5 Anchors

In our system we use anchors that define locations in the shared virtual space where avatars of participants, humanoid AI agents or objects and UI elements can be spawned. Such anchors are defined by a unique name and a position and orientation. As Augmented Reality SDKs also offer the possibility to define anchors in the physical space, we were aiming to explore the unification of virtual and augmented reality anchors. For example, we could create an AR anchor with the same name on a physical chair of each participant of the shared experience and to spawn a humanoid agent that would then appear in the AR anchor location as defined in each participant's physical space. As at the time of writing the integration of AR anchors in the AR foundations was still in very early stages, we did not manage to integrate this idea in the overall system. We have, nonetheless, created a separate dedicated app that enables us to explore the technical requirements, and still aim to add this functionality to our GuestXR Application before the end of the project.

² Quest 3 - Ballshooter / Mesh Export Tool. <https://jasonharron.github.io/>

2.6 Locomotion

It has been shown that presence, the sense of being in a virtual space, can be maintained better if the participant moves inside the virtual space by walking or walking in place, in the real space [5]. In order to animate the legs of the participant's avatar, they either have to be tracked or their movements have to be inferred from other trackers or input data. If the movements are inferred from trackers, then there are several ways in which the leg movements can be generated. In FinalIK³, they are either generated procedurally based on the estimated Centre Of Mass (COM) and Centre Of Pressure (COP) of the avatar (see *Figure 11*) or the movements are chosen from a set of animations in an animation blend tree⁴.

Figure 11 Centre of mass and centre of pressure points are used to estimate leg movements of the avatar.

A recent system proposed by Meta Reality Lab researchers is based on a machine learning approach in which reinforcement learning (RL) is used to map the leg movements from the sparse tracking data to a dataset of full body motion capture data [6]. This system is expected to improve the realism of estimated leg movements, but currently still suffers from unpredictable behaviour in edge cases. We want to investigate the feasibility of using a diffusion-based model on a standalone headset, which was recently published by Meta [7]

In [8] a system is presented that extracts body movements from video streams of additional cameras on the handheld controllers. The Meta Quest Pro hand controllers have 3 additional cameras per controller that could potentially be used in a similar way to also extract the participants' leg and body movements more accurately.

As the real spaces of the participants are likely to be of different size the system should allow techniques such as walking in place or redirected walking [9].

³ Inverse Kinematics solution for Unity. <https://assetstore.unity.com/packages/tools/animation/final-ik-14290>

⁴ Animation Blend Trees. Unity Manual. <https://docs.unity3d.com/Manual/class-BlendTree.html>

2.7 Teleportation

MRTK 2, the framework we use at the time of writing, has built in functionality for teleportation in VR. By teleportation we mean a point and click functionality with which the perspective of the participant is changed to the location that the participant points at. We have focused on making this functionality also available when embodied as an avatar but have found issues with the MRTK framework that would not allow us to move MRTKs internal perspective with that of the avatar, which would be required for the teleportation to work. In essence, teleportation would be equivalent with the kernel and overlap possibilities of space unification, as teleportation in the virtual space would act as a translation and or rotation of the physical space in the shared virtual space as proposed by Sra et al. in [10].

As a work around to move the local physical space in the shared virtual space, we found the possibility to re-calibrate the perspective of the headset (long pressing the oculus button), which re-centres the user's position and orientation to the current one. As pointed out in [10], scaling a smaller physical space to a larger virtual space resulted in the worst reported co presence as the movements of the participant in the smaller space is scaled to reach to the locations in the larger virtual space. We did not implement such movement scaling as this would have implications on the walking locomotion and the way it is shared, where an avatar representing a participant in a smaller space would have to move faster in the larger physical space of another participant and therefore would cause undesirable foot sliding.

2.8 Demonstration: A shared Jenga Game

To demonstrate the capabilities of the system required for this deliverable, such as natural walking and interacting through full body avatars through movement and voice we have developed a simple Jenga game in which wooden blocks are stacked, and the participants have to pull out blocks from the bottom to place them on top of the stack until the stack collapses.

Remote participants can naturally interact in AR by voice and body movements of their full body avatars. The stack of wooden blocks is controlled by Unity's physics engine so that they behave similarly to a real stack of wooden blocks in a Jenga game. The number of participants can vary between 1 and 8. Participants can move and orient their movement area within the shared space through re-calibration from different locations and orientations in their physical space. Screenshots of the gameplay are shown in *Figure 12-Figure 16*.

Figure 12 Five participants from VBW located in different places in Spain between Barcelona and Cadiz are testing the Jenga game embodied as full body avatars.

Figure 13 Participants can take the wood pieces as if they were grasping real objects with their hands. Facial expressions of participants with the Quest Pro are also shared as can be seen on the avatar in the left.

Figure 14 Participants can naturally kneel to reach pieces further down in the stack.

Figure 15 Physics simulation between the blocks gives the possibility for interaction with the objects and that the tower would collapse if the pieces are not balanced well.

Figure 16 A screenshot of the collapsed shared Jenga tower.

Example gameplay is also available as a video at:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=m8NIKul14c8>

3 Acoustics

In this section of the report, we describe our work on acoustic coherence between physical locations. One approach uses acoustic ray tracing and AR scene geometry capture, and the other approach uses neural networks to learn the acoustic properties as an audio style transfer problem.

3.1 Acoustic Matching Using Geometry from Meta Space Setup

Virtual sound sources in mixed reality must seamlessly blend with the user's real sound environment [11]. To achieve this, virtual audio synthesis must consider the room's acoustic properties, with room geometry being essential. Many VR spatialization tools, such as the Meta Audio SDK and Steam Audio, utilize ray tracing algorithms to calculate sound reflections based on geometry [12]. By integrating room geometry from the Meta Space Setup described earlier, acoustic simulations can more accurately replicate the real environment.

3.1.1 Demonstration

In this demonstration, we present a simple example of integrating room geometry into an acoustic simulation. We created a Unity scene with a speaking avatar placed in a shoebox-shaped room. The room's walls are designated as geometry objects for the ray tracing algorithm, which computes sound reflections. These geometry objects are tagged as dynamic to allow for real-time changes to the room during runtime.

Figure 17 View at the start of the application - the user sees and hears the avatar audio source augmented in the passthrough mode and a toggle "Match acoustics".

Figure 18 Adjusting the acoustic geometry (yellow shoebox room) to match the higher-level information from the Meta space setup functionality (light blue shoebox room). When the room is updated, acoustic properties change.

Before starting the experience, users must configure their current space using the Quest Headset. Once the experience begins, this room setup becomes accessible to the application. Currently, our demonstration is only applicable to shoebox-shaped rooms.

During the experience, users view their actual room through a passthrough mode, alongside an augmented speaking avatar and a "Match Acoustics" toggle. Initially, the avatar's audio is spatialized, and acoustic reflections are calculated using a default shoebox room model (yellow room in *Figure 18*).

When the user selects the "Match Acoustics" toggle, the shoebox model used for reflection calculations is adjusted to match the real room dimensions configured during setup (blue room in *Figure 18* represents the high-level information from the Meta Space Setup). This adjustment allows users to hear changes in the avatar's speech as the acoustic properties are updated to reflect the actual size of their room. The goal is to make the avatar's speech sound more natural, thereby enhancing the realism of the mixed reality experience.

However, to achieve a closer alignment between the simulated and real environments, it is important to consider more complex room geometries and obtain accurate acoustic specifications of room materials (e.g., walls, furniture, windows). These factors influence sound propagation as significantly as room geometry does.

3.2 Acoustic Matching as a Post-Processing Algorithm

Another approach, which is primarily a research topic rather than a practical real-time capable solution, involves developing algorithms to post-process simulated sound. These algorithms modify sound recorded or synthesized in acoustic space A to resemble that of space B, utilizing representations of space B such as photos or recordings [13], [14], [15], [16], [17]. Building on this approach, we developed a time-domain end-to-end acoustic space transfer method that matches the acoustic properties between two arbitrarily chosen reverberant signals [18].

Our method comprises three main components:

1. **Time-Domain Convolutional Encoder:** Extracts information about the acoustic space from the reference recording.
2. **Time-Domain Convolutional Encoder-Decoder:** Modifies the input signal to match the target acoustic properties.
3. **Conditioning Mechanism:** Ensures that information about the target space is utilized in the transformation process.

The objective of our approach is to address the following task: Given two reverberant speech signals $\mathbf{s}_1\mathbf{r}_1$ and $\mathbf{s}_2\mathbf{r}_2$, estimate the reverberant speech signal $\mathbf{s}_1\mathbf{r}_2$, where \mathbf{s}_1 and \mathbf{s}_2 represent distinct speech samples, and \mathbf{r}_1 and \mathbf{r}_2 represent different reverberation types. In other words, the goal is to modify the properties of the **content** signal $\mathbf{s}_1\mathbf{r}_1$ so that it sounds as if it originated from the acoustic space characterized by the **style** signal $\mathbf{s}_2\mathbf{r}_2$.

Figure 19 Deep-learning based approach to acoustic matching.

3.2.1 Demonstration

This demonstration utilizes a Jupyter notebook to showcase the deep learning method. Within the notebook, users can select various combinations of content and style sounds from the dataset, apply the acoustic matching transformation to each pair, and compare the results with the ground truth.

The demonstration illustrates the flexibility of the approach, enabling both de-reverberation and re-reverberation depending on the relationship between the style and content sounds. To listen to two selected audio examples, please visit: <https://youtu.be/7LxYMXLMWd0>.

Figure 20 Jupyter notebook to demonstrate acoustic matching approach.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this document we have discussed the technical aspects that were involved to demonstrate our results related to spatial and acoustic coherence. We discussed the details about movement and voice capture and the different methods that are used to create a coherent experience through physical simulation, light and acoustic integration.

We have described 3 demos. The first one is a shared Jenga game that illustrates all the capabilities of the system to create a shared experience in which participants can walk naturally and communicate through their full body avatars' body movements and through voice to work together interacting with physically simulated objects in a competitive game in augmented reality from different remote physical spaces.

We described a second demo that shows the possibility to use the geometric information of physical spaces to simulate the acoustic properties through acoustic ray tracing.

Finally, we described as a third demo some new research methods that model acoustic coherence between different physical spaces as a style transfer problem through neural networks that learn to convert audio from one physical space to another.

We have set our goals higher than set out in the proposal by aiming to exploit capabilities recently added to AR devices, such as the scanning of rooms and extraction of semantic information. However, we have found challenges regarding the integration of these capabilities with the full system for shared environments for which the required third-party software packages were not sufficiently well developed to integrate with the overall system. Nevertheless, we did explore these possibilities in dedicated applications and are aiming to integrate them in the final overall system.

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